

Supporting Information

High-throughput exploration of structural and electrochemical properties of the high entropy nitride system (Ti-Co-Mo-Ta-W)N

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Chemical composition of the (Ti-Co-Mo-Ta-W)N materials library deposited at 500 °C

Figure S 1: EDS composition maps of the (Ti-Co-Mo-Ta-W)N materials library deposited at 500 °C, normalized to metal elements. All maps use the same color scale ranging from 8 to 40 at.%. The figure in the upper center represents the target positions during co-sputter deposition.

Figure S 2: X-ray diffractograms and lattice parameters. The XRD diffractograms plotted as linescans for the library deposited at a) 300 and b) 500 °C. On the left side is the linescan from Ti-W-rich side (top) to Ta-rich side (bottom). On the right from Mo-rich at the top to Co-rich at the bottom. Visualization of the lattice parameters calculated from XRD patterns for the materials library deposited at c) 300 °C and d) 500 °C.

Cross sectional SEM images

Figure S 3: Cross section SEM images for thin film thickness measurements. The thin film thickness was measured exemplarily in five different regions using SE images. The measurement positions are marked on the photo at the top, the scale bar is the same for all images and shown in the lower right corner. The thin film thickness ranges from approximately 568 nm in the Co-rich region to 650 nm in the Ti- and W-rich region.

All LSVs

Figure S 4: All LSVs of the first cycle of OER activity measurements. All LSVs of the materials library deposited at a) 300°C and b) 500°C. The measured current is plotted in μA against the potential vs. RHE in mV.

Additional OER measurements

a)

current density at 1500 - current density at 1200
mV vs. RHE [mA cm^{-2}]

Figure S 5: OER activity during several cycles of OER activity measurements. For both materials libraries four measurement areas located on the line on the pre-oxidation map were chosen for additional measurements. In each of those measurement areas two cyclic voltammograms in the potential range 1-1.85 V vs. RHE were conducted separated by the ten cycles in the potential range of 1-1.6 V vs. RHE. The oxidation peaks are decreasing with each cycle, suggesting the irreversible oxidation of the thin films.